

Transition Plan for ASD children from preschool to kindergarten.

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Abstract:

A systematic survey of quantitative assessments of preschool children with autism spectrum is presented as representing their identity as an independent culture with a right to live in the mainstream world, accepted as they are. This calls for an assessment of social, communicative and locomotion motor skills and the minimal comprehension and cognitive skills needed to inhabit this world with the minimal accommodations. Stakeholders in a transition and the mainstream IEP are identified with a cautionary note on the inadequacies of a curricular approach in IEP, in lieu of alternative schooling. Holistic approaches from the Himalayan viewpoint, and other viewpoints of informal Catholic, Islamic, Judaist, Buddhist, Vedic and other major theologies are presented for alternative schooling as a transition strategy.

Keywords: Alternative schooling, transition strategy, stakeholders, quantitative methods.

Introduction.

A formal curricular education from preschool, marks a learning path termed s-coolie or scoolie by the author, denoting a life long trajectory of learning and transition for normal and autistic individuals. While more normal scoolies, end up in a technological slavery, they end up in 30 year bondages to mortgages and automotive financing, and increased materialism, with the American Dream of success defined in a high paying career and a two garage home, with two or more automobiles, taking decades to own.

With this mindset, expectations are set for a preschool autistic child with this definition of

materialism, as a definition of success. A definition of drudgery and impossible targets, every autistic child would shy away from, but given the very high expectations of society, parents and the community, they remain forced in a transition to this learning path, a path, the author would hesitate in defining strategies for.

The main stakeholders

- Psychiatrist, occupational therapist, speech therapist
- Freeborn lobby representatives, child rights, unicef, free thinkers and alternative school representatives.
- Teaching community representatives, including every teacher involved.
- Social net for the child, in case he turns into an anarchist at such a young age.
- Building supervisor and maintenance staff.
- Fire rescue and ambulance service, paramedics.
- Building Principal(private communication)
- Martial arts instructor.
- Native American Spokesman.
- Senator and local government representative.
- Investor for baby bonds and “Child as Investment,” “investing in the future today”, for the child's protection.
- Insurance agent, you are in “good hands”.

Quantitative factors needed by the stakeholders in readiness evaluation.

The need for special education and interventions in a successful transition of ASD students to school from preschool programs, needs an evaluation of school readiness, a transition from the informal to a curricular training.

Literature, such as, Marsh A[1], indicates quantitative criteria for readiness based on published literature.

Out of 238 papers on the Google Scholar and Pubmed databases, inclusion criteria were readiness in transition and parental and teacher expectations, a total of

Four papers on readiness and four on teachers and parents expectations were shortlisted after abstract and data of full text analysis from 28 papers are presented.

Fig 1: PRISMA Diagram for a systematic survey on readiness and expectations, and strategies for transitioning from preschool to curricular kindergarten.

In Crane[2], the measurements used are, DECA and ELAP, (SRUSS), ESI-K, DIBELS, SAT-10, Klubnik, Murphy[3] use Stanford-Binet Intelligence Scales, Fifth Edition (SB5; Roid, 2003), Childhood Autism Rating Scale, Second Edition (CARS-2; Schopler, Van Bourgondien, Wellman, and Love, 2010), Vineland Adaptive Behaviour Scale, Bracken Basic Concept Scale Third Edition: Receptive (Bracken, 2006)

Matthews[4] (2014) use Background information; History of child care; Friendship quality; School readiness - parent report of social-emotional and self-help school readiness; Theory of Mind (ToM Developmental Scale (Wellman et al, 20016; Wellman and Liu, 2004); Appearance-reality (Wellman and Liu, 2004); Second-order false belief (Targer-Flusberg and Sullivan, 1994); School readiness - Cognitive/motor (Cognitive: Concept tasks; Cognitive: Language tasks; Motor tasks); Verbal ability [Peabody Picture Vocabulary Test-III (Dunn and Dunn, 1997)]

Waddington and Reed[5] (2009) use Gilliam Autism Rating Scale (GARS; Gilliam, 1995), Vineland Adaptive Behavior Scale, Mainstreaming Social Skills Questionnaire (MSSQ: Salend and Lutz, 1984), Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ: Goodman, 1987).

The anti-ABA Lobby.¹

The middle ground adopted by the author is the right of neurodiversity and distancing the neurotypical, assessments indicate strengths, which spectrum children adopt, a weakness could be viewed a strength and a strength a weakness, while essential communication, locomotion and cognition in a preschool child can be gauged by the quantitative methods described below, the need for transitioning is outdated by technological advancements.

Open BCI is a EEG based BCI cap^{2 2-4} that allows for communication and complete self sufficiency for an neurodiverse or neurotypical child, many other solutions outdate the need for IEP or a transition program, with digital literacy through MooC based courses and flip learning with videos and images emphasised.

Technology provides synthesisia aids, wearables to augment life and rich AR and SAR technology, providing adaptations and accommodations to fulfil one basic right of the neurodiverse to live in both worlds, the creative hidden world, they so much protect from the mainstream and the world of the neurotypical.

The Addendum includes a Table reproduced from (Crane[2]), a survey on readiness studies, with the results obtained.

Transition Strategy.

The need for the minimal learned skills of spoken language and mobility, and learning and cognition skills calls for acquisition of these basic skills for the recognition of autism as an independent culture implementing the right for spectrum patients to successfully live in the mainstream. While several alternative schooling strategies are more applicable to the target autism audience, there are so many constraints to curricular education of space and time which make the transition challenging and near impossible. Space constraints and attention span constraints make a transition nearly impossible for most students needing special schools and spectrum specific schooling in informal education. The limited cognitive and communication capabilities, would require the increased use of technological accommodation, requiring alternative schooling.

A drastic measure of legal residential schooling for spectrum students, could lead to stolen childhoods in special schools, isolated from the social community and reared like pedigree guard dogs, brainwashed in ideologies and approaches could be a dark scenario depicting the state of formal education.

In the continued insistence on a formal curriculum and a strategy for transition, much like requiring the University of Minnesota Gopher to attend classes and transition successfully, the timeless stick and carrot approach, ABA and reinforcement learning coupled with corporeal

punishment may be reintroduced. Reinforcements are set in didactic pedagogies, while teachers use subversion, dominance on innocent spectrum patients, who fail to grasp any need for the transition, often leading to high dropout rates and disappointment. Even the successful land in tainted vocational careers, rarely succeeding in self employment or a professional setting unlike students with alternative schooling based on Metta⁵ and formulations of Earth friendly education⁶ based on timeless spirituality of universal unconditional love,⁷ as preached in the Catholic, Islam, Buddhist, Judaist and Vedic spiritualities. It remains to be seen if students from these alternative schooling would contribute to the mainstream, where natural education fills all those voids in the education and transitioning of spectrum students.

Conclusions and future work.

Quantitative methods are introduced for the minimal skills needed, as formal or informal education and strategies for a transition to curricular schooling is compared to a transition to alternative schooling. The pitfalls of the inadequacy of curricular education are explored in the unnecessary bondage to technology rather than an emphasis of synergy and design. The resultant scoolies are part of a life of investment instruments, with a financial security tied to stakeholders, from the insurance and inventor lobbies, along with the poorly paid teaching lobby. It is thus emphasized, that given the choices, and leveraging the strengths, of the child, the learning path of maturity and a well rounded education is more outdoors and in alternative schooling with droids⁸ rather than the programmed robotics of curricular practice. The freedom of the meadow and the entomology stands taller than a sentence in a classroom.

Addendum:

Table 1

Summary of studies examining school transition for children with autism spectrum

disorder **Author (yr)** **Country** **Sample** **Intervention Measures** **Findings**

School readiness	United States	disabilities	received special education services	(DECA; LeBuffe and Naglieri,
Crane[14] (2010)	91 children with ASD; 1338 children with ASD and other	Children		

1999); (LAP-D; Nehring, Nehring, Bruni and Randolph, 1992), Early Learning Accomplishment Profile (ELAP; Glover, Preminger and Sanford, 2002), (SRUSS), ESI-K, DIBELS, SAT-10 Children with ASD (and developmental delay group) showed the slowest gains over time in the language, cognitive and fine motor domains. Children with ASD had significantly lower scores on the initiative, self-control and attachment	scales than all groups except the developmental delay group Klubnik, Murphy, Campbell, Reed and Warner Metzger[15] (2014) United States Exp group: 76 children with ID and ASD/ID group. ASD, M = 53.60 mo. ASD/ID group had Comp Group: 47 children with ID, M = 59.25 mo Standford-Binet Intelligence Scales, Fifth Edition (SB5; Roid, 2003), Childhood Autism Rating Scale, Second Edition (CARS-2; Schopler, Van Bourgondien, Wellman, and Love, 2010), Vineland Adaptive Behaviour Scale, Bracken Basic	Concept Scale Third Edition: Receptive (Bracken, 2006) Receptive understanding of self-/social awareness concepts was significantly lower for the children with ID and ASD/ID group. ASD/ID group had significantly higher school readiness scores than the ID group. The ASD/ID group's the School Readiness Composite was greater than their Self/Social-Awa reness substest Matthews[16] (2014) United States Exp: 63 children with a parent-reported diagnosis of ASD, M = 5.16 yr (4-6 yr). Comp Group: 33 TD	children, M = 5.35 yr (4-6 yr) Background information; History of child care; Friendship quality; School readiness - parent report of social-emotional and self-help school readiness; Theory of Mind (ToM Developmental Scale (Wellman et al, 20016; Wellman and Liu, 2004); Appearance-reality (Wellman and Liu, 2004); Second-order false belief (Targer-Flusberg and Sullivan, 1994); School readiness - Cognitive/motor (Cognitive: Cognitive:	Language tasks; Motor tasks); Verbal ability Children with ASD, experiencing centre-based care was not associated with cognitive/motor school readiness, social-emotional school readiness, or level of self-help school readiness. Children with ASD who demonstrated more advanced ToM performance had higher cognitive/motor school readiness and levels of self-help school readiness. Both groups, children with more positive friendship quality had higher levels of
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	children with ASD, Baseline, M = 6.7 yr (4.3-10.5 yr), Comp Group (Treatment as usual (TAU)): 15 children with ASD, Baseline, M = 9.1 yr (5.2-15.0 yr)	inclusion in a mainstream kindergarten; based on ABA; 5 skill areas: Academic literacy, communication, listening, social speaking, self-management, school self-sufficiency, community, physical/motor. Individualised. Teaching takes place 1:1 or small groups	[Peabody Picture Difficulties Vocabulary Questionnaire (SDQ: Goodman, 1987) and Dunn, 1997)] Gilliam Autism Rating Scale (GARS; Gilliam, 1995), Vineland Adaptive Behavior Scale, Mainstreaming Social Skills Questionnaire (MSSQ: Salend and Lutz, 1984), Strengths and	socialisation, and daily living skills (not compared with social-emotional comparison group just and self-help school readiness improvements within group) with these skills continuing at mainstream school attending mainstream schools demonstrated improvements in communication,
Waddington and Reed[17] (2009) (Study 2)				
United Kingdom Exp group (PIRKS): 12				

Parents'/teachers' views/experiences of school transition process

Beamish, Bryer and Klieve[18] (2014)	practices online survey: 36		Themes: Child visit, Parent information, Teacher sharing, Placement identification, Decision support, Sending teacher,	Support identification, Evaluation administrator, Visit support, Peer preparation All 36 practices highly endorsed
Australia 91 intervention and advisory (specialised preschool) teachers Transition	practices items identified from review of literature (including Forest et al, 2004).			
Denkyirah and MAgbeke[2] (2010)	preschool teachers. Comp group: 82	teachers from Ghana Survey developed from	Forest et al, 2004. Themes: Timing for planning and	preparation; Sharing information with family;
United States Exp group: 306	preschool			

Discussing placement with family; Helping families find school and community resources; Preparing and receiving school and teachers; Relationships between sending and receiving schools; Assistive technology; Home visit; Parent taring All themes endorsed by teachers in both countries Fontil and Petrakos[4] (2015) United States Parents of 10 children (aged 53.8-87.4 mo) with or suspected of having	ASD Interview questions adapted from Kindergarten Transition Parent Interview - Preschool (Pianta and Kraft-Sayre, 2003). Themes: child's experiences at school, their peer contact, their activities at home, and parents' personal activities with the school. Measure of Processes of Care (MPOC-20; King, King and Rosenbaum, 2004) Empathy, Caring, and Understanding: Relationships with	preschool teachers more positive than with kindergarten teachers. Knowledge and Expertise: More sharing of information with parents at preschool than school. Less educational opportunities and resources at school than preschool Quintero and McIntyre[1] (2011) United States Exp group: Parents and teachers of 19 children with ASD (M = 58.84 mo). Comp group: Parents and teachers of 76 children with	Developmental Difficulties, M = 58.66 mo Time 1 - end of preschool; Parents: Family Experiences and Involvement in Transition (FEIT; McIntyre et al, 2007); Preschool teachers: Teachers' Perceptions on Transition (TPOT), Open Ended Questions in TPOT. Time 2 - kindergarten entry; Parents: Family Experiences and Involvement in Transition (FEIT; McIntyre et al, 2007) Teachers' Perceptions on Transition:	Teachers significantly more likely to report higher concerns (some, many, or very many concerns) for children with ASD than children with DD. Teachers endorsed visiting students' assigned kindergarten classroom more for children in the ASD group than the DD group. Parent Involvement: Parents of DD group reported participating in a transition planning meeting significantly more than parents in the ASD group. Parents of DD group reported to have received written
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communication
 regarding the
 transition from
 the kindergarten
 program
 significantly
 more than
 parents in the
 ASD group

Protective and risk
 factors in first year

of school

Charman et al [19]
 (2004)

United Kingdom
 Cohort 1: 73 children
 with ASD, Cohort 2:
 52 children

with ASD; Baseline
 both cohorts M =
 56.6 mo

Vineland
 Adaptive
 Behavior
 Scales-Screen
 Version

(VABS-S;
 Sparrows, 2000),

Social
 Communication
 Questionnaire (SCQ;

Berument et al,
 1999),

Autism
 Treatment
 Evaluation
 Checklist

(ATEC; Rimland and
 Edelson,
 1999)

Group made more
 rapid
 development
 progress in the 11
 mo in school than
 they had preschool.

Pattern of
 change on the ATEC
 was

mixed. On the social,
 language and

communication
 subscale the scores
 did
 significantly reduce
 over
 time. The best
 developmental
 progress was made
 by
 children with better
 communication skills
 at the
 outset
 Esienhower,
 Blacher and
 Bush [12] (2015)
 United States
 166 children with
 ASD (M = 5 yr 8
 mo, 4-7 yr) and one

parent per child
 Demographics,
 ADOS,
 abbreviated
 WPPSI-II,
 Student-Teacher
 Relationship
 Scale (STRS; Pianta,
 2001),
 Caregiver-Teacher
 Report Form and
 Teacher
 Report Form (CTRF
 and TRF; Achenbach
 and Rescoria, 2000,
 2001)
 High
 externalising
 behaviour

predicted poor STR
 and was not
 moderate by
 cognitive
 abilities.
 Jahromi, Bryce and
 Swanson [20]
 (2013)
 United States
 Exp group: 20
 children with
 HFASD, M = 58.95
 mo.
 Comp group: 20
 typically developing
 children, M = 50.20
 mo
 Measures:
 Preschool
 Language Scale 4

(PLS-4; Zimmerman, Steiner, and Pond, 2002), Differential Abilities Scale II (DAS-II; Elliot, 2007), Autism Diagnostic Interview-Revise d (ADI-R; Lord et al, 1994), Social Communication Questionnaire (SCQ; Rutter et al, 2003), Emotion Regulation Checklist (ER Checklist; Shields and Cicchetti, 1997), Day/Night Task (Gerstadt, Hong, and Diamond, 1994), Behavior Rating Inventory of Executive Function-Preschool Children with HFA (Diamond, 1994), typically developing peers. Behavioural engagement: children with HFA had significantly less cooperative and independent participation. Emotional engagement: ol Version (BRIEF-P; Gioia, Isquith, Guy, Kenworthy, 2000), Parent-child joint engagement states and child-initiated joint engagement (Bakeman and Adamson, 1984), Child Behavior Questionnaire-S hort Form (CBQ-SF; Putnam and Rothbart, 2006; Rothbart, Ahadi, Hershey, and Fisher, 2001), School Liking and Avoidance Questionnaire (Ladd et al, 2000), parent-report version of the Teacher Rating Scale of School Adjustment (Buhs and Ladd, 2001), Child Behavior Scale greater prosocial behaviour with peers

<p>Prino, Pasta, Giovanna, Gastaldi and Longobardi[23] (2016)</p>	<p>85.75 mo; 18 children with Down Syndrome, M = 85.75 mo, teacher or assistant per child (n = 32). Comp group: 128 TD children (classmates), M = 78.54 mo</p>	<p>(CBS; Ladd and Profilet, 1996) Student-Teacher Relationship Scale (STRS; Pianta, 2001)</p>	<p>with Down Syndrome and their TD classmates. Teachers' reported significantly higher conflict scores and significantly lower closeness scores for children with ASD than their TD peers</p>
<p>Italy Exp group: 14 children with ASD, M =</p>	<p>children (classmates), M = 78.54 mo</p>	<p>No difference between teachers' perceptions of children</p>	
<p>Sparapani <i>et al</i>[21] (2016) United States 196 children with ASD, M = 6.36 yr ADOS, Stanford-Binet Intelligence Scale - 5th Ed (SB-5; Roid, 2003), Peabody Picture</p>	<p>Vocabulary Test - 4th Ed (PPVT-4; Dunn and Dunn, 2007), Expressive One Word Vocabulary Picture Test - 4th Ed (EOWVPT-4; Brownwell, 2000), Social Skills Rating</p>	<p>system (SSRS; Gresham and Elliott, 1990), Teacher Report Form (TRF; Achenbach and Rescorla, 2001), 60-min classroom observations. Five themes: Emotional Regulation, Classroom</p>	<p>No difference between children in general education and special education classes. Students spent less than 50% of time in adirected well-regulated state, productively and independently participating in classroom activities. Students only responded to half of verbal bids for interaction, infrequently communication, and rarely used generative language</p>

	range 54 to 72 mo (M = 63.89 mo)	based on the United Kingdom Participation, Social Connectedness, Initiating Communication, and Flexibility	Positive changes were observed for the majority of children enrolled in the ABA class - moderate to large-sized effects found for standardized test outcomes after 1 yr of intervention. Outcomes for ABA class were positive compared with the treatment as usual	(2015)	shares; (2) Comments about one's own play; (3) Comments about others' play; (4) Niceties, <i>e.g.</i> , please, thank-you; and (5) play organizers, <i>e.g.</i> , to give ideas about setting up games and rules	
Grindle et al[10] (2012)	School-based comprehensive behavioural intervention features: (1) Parents generalize skills at home; (2) One-to-one intervention at desks in a shared classroom; (3) Education for a maximum of 6 h per day for 38 wk of year; (4) Matched school timetable; (5) Generalise skills to mainstream classes; and (6)	IQ: Stanford-Binet Intelligence Scale -Fourth Edition or Leiter International Performance Scale-Revised; Vineland Adaptive Behavior Scale-Survey Form (VABS); ABLLS/ABLLS R assesses skills such as effective social and communicative functioning, imitation, and cooperation	majority of children enrolled in the ABA class - moderate to large-sized effects found for standardized test outcomes after 1 yr of intervention. Outcomes for ABA class were positive compared with the treatment as usual	Exp group (Peer Networks Intervention): 56 children with ASD, baseline: Age M = 5.8 yr. Comp group (EAU): 39 children with ASD baseline: Age M = 5.8 yr National Curriculum Peer network intervention: peer training and direct instruction. Five skills: (1) Requests and	United States	Comments about others' play; (4) Niceties, <i>e.g.</i> , please, thank-you; and (5) play organizers, <i>e.g.</i> , to give ideas about setting up games and rules
United Kingdom, 4-5 yr Exp group (ABA): 11 children with ASD, baseline: Age range 43 to 68 mo (M = 58.2 mo). Comp group [Education as usual (EAU)]: 18 children with ASD baseline: Age						Dependent measures from direct observations consisted Clinical Evaluation of Language Fundamentals-4, Core Language Scores (CELF-4; Semel et al 2003); the Vineland
				Kamps et al[11]		

Adaptive group					
Behaviour Scale participants.					
Teacher Standard scores				Modest	
Report-Communication subtest	for language performance and communication (VABS; Sparrow et al 2006); and teacher ratings of classroom social behaviours [The Teacher Impression Scale (TIS); Odom and McConnell, 1997]	192 children with ADOS, ASD, M = 6.1 yr (5-8 yr), grades Kindergarten to second	Differential Ability Scales-Second Edition (DAS-II; Elliott, 2009), Adaptive Behavior Assessment System-Second Ed (ABAS-ii; Harrison and Oakland, 2003), Pervasive Developmental Disorder Behavior Inventory (PDDBI; Cohen and Sudhalter, 2005)-Teacher Form intervention group than for comparison group children	increases in global cognitive ability scores. Negligible changes in social functioning (McKeating[28] (2014) United States Exp group: 39 children with ASD, M = 6.21 yr (5-7 yr). Comp Group: 39 children with other disabilities, M = 6.26 yr (5-8 yr) teachers of children in	sample) Children received Itinerant, supplemental or full-time special education services Inclusive Classroom Profile (ICP; Soukakou, 2010), Autism Evaluation Treatment Checklist (AETC; Rimland and Edelson, 1999), Teacher Perception Survey (TPS) Children receiving full
Peer intervention group improved more in initiations to peers during non-treatment social probes and during generalization probes in natural settings than the comparison	Locke et al[26] (2014)	(STAR), which incorporates discrete trial training (DDT, Smith 2001, from ABA), pivotal response training (PRT; Koegel et al, 1989) and functional routines			

time special (5-8 yr), grades Disorder changes in DAS trained teachers.
education Kindergarten to Behavior scores. Higher Curriculum
services made second Inventory social anxiety addressed core
substantially Strategies for (PDDBI; Cohen symptoms and deficits of
greater progress Teaching based and Sudhalter, increase in children with
in sociability and on Autism 2005)-Teacher student age ASD using
behaviour, but Research Form, Child significantly evidence-based
not in (STAR), which Symptom predicted a strategies and
communication, incorporates Inventory-4 decrease in behaviour
sensory or discrete trial (CSI-4; Gdaow DAS scores management
cognitive training (DDT, and Sprafkin, Sainato et al[27] Leiter
abilities, than Smith 2001, 2002) (2015) International
children from ABA), Modest mean United States Performance
receiving pivotal response change in DAS Exp group Scale-Revised
supplemental and training (PRT; GCA scores. (Inclusive (Leiter-R; Roid,
itinerant services. Koegel et al, Several kindergarten and Miller,
All children, 1989) and measures of program): 41 2002); Kaufman
regardless of functional adaptive children with Test of
placement routines. behaviour; ASD, baseline: Educational
achieved higher ADOS, functional Age M = 75.7 Achievement,
sociability Differential academics, mo. Comp Second Edition
scores at Ability health and group (Eclectic (KTEA-II; Adaptive
post-test. Scales–Second safety, intervention): 21 Kaufman and Behavior
Teacher Edition (DAS-II; self-direction, children Kaufman, 2004); Scales-Classroom
perceptions of Elliott, 2009), social skills, and with ASD, The Test of m Edition
inclusion Adaptive the overall baseline: Age M Development (Sparrow, Balla,
Behavior adaptive = 74.1 mo Language and Cicchetti,
predicted higher Assessment composite Experimental Development 1985)
ATEC scores System-Second predicted group (TOLD-P: 3; Experimental
Pellecchia *et* Ed (ABAS-ii; changes in DAS participated in group made
al[25] (2016) Harrison and scores. Social general education classroom significant gains
United States Oakland, 2003), anxiety classroom taught by in nonverbal
152 children with Pervasive symptoms predicted intelligence,
ASD, M = 6.0 yr Developmental predicted academic

achievement, and Behavior
 language scores
 compared with
 comparison
 group.
 Comparison
 group exhibited
 either no
 improvement or
 decreases. Both
 model and
 comparison
 groups
 demonstrated
 similar
 improvement in
 pre- and
 post-test
 outcomes on the
 Vineland
 Adaptive

Basics', a CAI
 program that
 includes
 computer
 lessons and
 natural
 environment
 activities
 (Connection
 Activities) for
 developmental
 ages 2-7 yr. The
 student is taught
 in a discrete
 trial format
 where they
 receive
 reinforcement for
 correct
 responses.
 Treatment

group used
 TeachTown:
 Basics for
 approximately 20
 min a day on
 school days
 over three
 months
 Peabody Picture
 Vocabulary Test,
 3rd Edition
 (PPVT; Dunn
 and Dunn),
 Expressive
 Vocabulary Test
 (EVT, Williams,
 1997), The
 Brigance
 Inventory of
 Early
 Development

(Brigance, 2004),
 Childhood
 Autism Rating
 Scale (CARS),
 Ongoing
 Automatic Data
 Collection
 (TeachTown:
 Basics)
 Children in the
 TeachTown:
 Basics group
 performed
 better across all
 language and
 cognitive
 outcome
 measures than the
 children in the
 control
 group.

Additionally,
 students who
 used
 TeachTown:
 Basics
 demonstrated
 significant
 progress overall
 in the software
 and those
 students who
 used the
 program for more
 time
 demonstrated
 larger gains
 within the
 software and in
 outcome
 measures

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Footnote: Other research populations examined separately not reported in this systematic review. DECA: Devereux Early Childhood Assessment; LAP-D: Learning Accomplishment Profile-Diagnostic; SRUSS: School Readiness Uniform Screening System; ASD: Autism spectrum disorder.

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